

Redistribution Reactions Involving Lithium Aluminium Hydride and Lithium Tetraphenylaluminate

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Redistribution reactions involving LiAlH_4 and LiAlPh_4 were performed by mixing the reagents in appropriate ratios. The products: LiAlH_3Ph , $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$ and LiAlHPh_3 were isolated and characterized by elemental analysis, infrared and nmr spectroscopy and DTA-TGA analysis. These products were also prepared by the reaction of PhLi with $\text{AlH}_n\text{Ph}_{3-n}$ (where $n=1-3$) in diethylether. Also PhAlH_2 and Ph_2AlH were prepared by the reaction of Ph_2Al and AlH_3 in both diethyl ether and THF in the appropriate stoichiometric ratios.

WE have been engaged in reactions of lithium aluminium hydride with various main group metal organic compounds, e. g., phenyllithium¹, diphenyl magnesium² and lithium triphenylmagnesiato³. In order to help characterize the products of the above reactions, it was deemed necessary to prepare the expected by-products of these reactions i.e., $\text{LiAlH}_n\text{R}_{3-n}$ (where $n=1-3$) by an independent method. For this reason, we studied the reaction of LiAlPh_4 and LiAlH_4 in diethylether by following the progress of the reaction by ir and nmr spectroscopy and isolating the intermediate products. Zakharkin and Ivanov⁴ in 1964 reported the reaction of alkali metals and their hydrides with triphenylaluminium and reported the preparation of lithium triphenylaluminium hydride. However, the product was not well characterized.

Experimental

Apparatus: Reactions were performed under dry nitrogen at the bench or in a glove box equipped with a recirculating system using manganese oxide to remove oxygen. Infrared spectra were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer 620 spectrophotometer using KBr and CsI liquid or mull cells. NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian A-60 in ether solvent. The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of LiAlPh_4 was obtained on a Philips-Norelco X-ray unit using a 114.6 mm camera with nickel filtered Cu-K_α radiation. The sample was sealed in 0.5 mm capillary and exposed to X-rays for 6 hr. The 'd' spacings were read on a precalibrated scale equipped with a viewing apparatus. Line intensities were estimated visually.

Analyses: Gas analyses were accomplished by hydrolysis of samples with HCl on a standard

vacuum line equipped with a Toepler pump. Aluminium was determined by adding excess EDTA and back-titrating with standard zinc acetate at pH 4 in 50% ethanol with dithizone as an indicator. Lithium was determined by flame photometry. Phenyl groups present in the complexes were determined by hydrolyzing the samples with water and analyzing the filtrate for benzene by glc using an S.E. 30 column at 70°. Mesitylene was used as the solvent and hexanol was used as the internal standard.

Materials: Solvents were distilled immediately prior to use over LiAlH_4 (ether) or NaAlH_4 (THF, benzene and mesitylene). Phenyl lithium was prepared in benzene diluent by the reaction of iodobenzene with *n*-butyllithium dissolved in hexane. The solid product was dissolved in ether, recrystallized at -78° , redissolved in freshly distilled ether and standardized by Watson and Eastham analysis⁵.

It was observed that phenyllithium cleaves diethyl ether at room temperature to give the product $\text{Li}_2(\text{OEt})\text{Ph}$. Ether cleavage could be slowed down by keeping the solution at -15° .

Triphenylaluminium⁶ was prepared by refluxing a mixture of diphenylmercury and aluminium chips in toluene for 40 hr and filtering the resulting mixture hot through glass wool under nitrogen pressure. The product was recrystallized in hot toluene and dried under reduced pressure (0.05 mm) for 1 hr at 60°.

Lithium aluminium hydride (LiAlH_4) was obtained from Venron, Metal Hydrides Division. A solution was prepared by refluxing LiAlH_4 in ether overnight followed by filtration through a glass-fritted funnel using dried Celite Analytical

Filter-Aid (Johns-Mansville). The clear solution was standardized by aluminium analysis.

Lithium tetraphenylaluminate (LiAlPh_4) was prepared by the addition of phenyllithium in ether to triphenylaluminium in ether with continuous stirring at 0° over a period of several hr. A viscous insoluble layer separated from the ether which crystallized from solution overnight. The white solid was soluble in tetrahydrofuran, but insoluble in diethyl ether. Analysis of the white solid gave the following results: Calcd. for $\text{LiAl}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4$; Li:Al:Ph=1.0:1.0:4.0. Found; 1.00:1.06:4.10.

X-ray powder diffraction data for LiAlPh_4 showed the following lines: 8.5 s, 6.8 w, 6.0 w-m, 5.4 vw, 4.8 vw, 4.4 vs, 4.15 s, 3.8 w, 3.25 m-s, 2.95 m, 2.82 w, 2.76 w, 2.63 w, 2.55 w, 2.43 w, 2.3 vc, 2.25 vw, 2.13 vw, 2.05 vw, 2.00 vw, 1.90 w, 1.78 w, 1.58 w.

Redistribution of LiAlH_4 and LiAlPh_4 as determined by infrared analysis: A 0.615 M solution of LiAlH_4 in ether was added in increments to a magnetically stirred slurry of LiAlPh_4 in ether at room temperature. When the ratio of LiAlH_4 to LiAlPh_4 was 1:3 a clear solution resulted. After each addition the solution was stirred for 1 hr at room temperature. Infrared spectra were obtained by withdrawing samples of the solutions under nitrogen via syringe. The additions were continued until LiAlH_4 was in excess. Fig. 1 shows the infrared spectra obtained in this study.

Fig. 1. Infrared spectra of solutions obtained by adding LiAlH_4 to LiAlPh_4 in diethyl ether in ratios (1) 1:3, (2) 1:1, (3) 3:1, (4) pure LiAlH_4 .

Preparation of LiAlH_3Ph : To a slurry of LiAlPh_4 (1.78 g; 5.2 mmoles) in ether was added 37.6 ml of 0.615 M solution of LiAlH_4 in ether (15.6 mmoles) at room temperature with continuous stirring. A clear solution resulted and the reaction mixture was stirred for an additional hr. The excess ether was removed under reduced pressure to give a viscous product which on standing at room temperature for 5 days produced crystals. Elemental analysis of the crystals gave the following ratios: Li:Al:H:Ph:ether = 1.02:1.00:3.03:0.97:2.10. Calcd. for $\text{LiAlH}_3\text{Ph}\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ = 1.00:1.00:3.00:1.00:2.00. The infrared spectrum in ether was similar to the spectrum shown in Fig. 1.

Preparation of $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$: To a slurry of LiAlPh_4 (2.839 g; 8.30 mmoles) in ether was added dropwise 20 ml of 0.615 M solution of LiAlH_4 in ether (8.30 mmoles) with constant stirring. This reaction mixture was stirred for 1 hr after a clear solution was obtained. The ether was removed under vacuum producing a pasty mass which crystallized after keeping for 3 days at room temperature. Elemental analysis gave the following ratios: Li:Al:H:Ph:Et₂O = 1.02:1.00:2.06:1.98:1.94. Calcd. for $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2\cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ = 1.00:1.00:2.00:2.00:2.00.

Preparation of LiAlHPh_3 : To a slurry of LiAlPh_4 (6.26 g; 12.45 mmoles) in ether was added dropwise 10.0 ml of 0.615 M solution (4.15 mmoles) of LiAlH_4 in ether. The resulting solution was stirred for 1 hr followed by removal of excess solvent under vacuum. When about 10 ml of ether remained, a white crystalline solid appeared which was separated by decantation, washed with ether and dried at room temperature under reduced pressure (0.05 mm) for 15 min. The crystalline product then changed to a viscous product. When freshly distilled ether was added to this viscous product, it again changed to a crystalline solid. The solid was separated and dried at 0° for 1 hr under vacuum (0.05 mm) and then analyzed. Elemental analysis gave the following ratio: Li:H:Ph:ether = 1.05:1.00:0.97:3.03:4.04. Calcd. for $\text{LiAlHPh}_3\cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ = 1.00:1.00:1.00:3.00:4.00.

Redistribution reaction of AlH_3 with AlPh_3 in ratios (i) 1:2, (ii) 2:1 in THF and diethyl ether.

(i) Reaction of AlH_3 with AlPh_3 in 1:2 ratio.

(a) In THF: To a well-stirred solution of Ph_3Al (10.0 mmoles) in THF (30 ml) was added dropwise 5.0 mmoles of AlH_3 solution in 15 ml of THF. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 hr at room temperature and the solution analyzed. Anal: Calcd. for AlHPh_2 . Al:H:Ph = 1.00:1.00:2.00. Found: 1.00:0.94:2.03. IR showed a strong band at 1782 cm^{-1} due to $\nu\text{Al-H}$ stretching. NMR analysis of the solution showed two multiplets due to the *ortho* (δ 7.7 ppm) and *meta-para* (δ 7.19 ppm) protons of the phenyl groups downfield to the THF signals, in the ratio of 2:3.

(b) *In diethyl ether*: When 7.0 mmoles of AlH_3 solution in diethyl ether (20 ml) was added to a well-stirred slurry of Ph_3Al (14.0 mmoles) in 30 ml of diethyl ether, a clear solution resulted in 15 min of stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for approximately 10 hr and analyzed. Anal: Calcd. for AlHPh_2 . Al:H:Ph = 1.00:1.00:2.00. Found: 1.00:0.97:2.02. The infrared spectrum of the solution showed the presence of $\nu\text{Al-H}$ stretching at 1865 cm^{-1} .

(ii) *Reaction of AlH_3 with Ph_3Al in 2:1 ratio.*

(a) *In THF*: 9.4 mmoles of AlH_3 solution in THF (25 ml) was added to a well-stirred solution of Ph_3Al (4.7 mmoles) in THF (20 ml) at room temperature and the reaction mixture stirred. The completion of the reaction was monitored by the complete disappearance of $\nu\text{Al-H}$ at 1760 cm^{-1} (due to AlH_3) and its appearance at 1770 cm^{-1} (due to PhAlH_2). The solution was analyzed. Anal: Calcd. for AlH_2Ph . Al:H:Ph = 1.00:2.00:1.00. Found: 1.00:1.90:1.03; An nmr spectrum of the product in THF showed two sets of multiplets centered at δ 7.73 ppm (due to *ortho* protons of the phenyl groups) and 7.23 ppm (due to *meta-para* protons of the phenyl groups) in the ratio 2:3.

(b) *In diethyl ether*: When the above reaction was carried out in diethyl ether solution, a clear solution resulted. Analysis of this solution showed that it contained Al, H, and Ph in ratios 1.00:1.93:1.01. An infrared spectrum of the reaction solution showed the presence of $\nu\text{Al-H}$ at 1845 cm^{-1} .

Reaction of PhLi with $\text{AlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(3-n)}$ in diethyl ether.

A diethyl ether solution of freshly prepared phenyllithium was added to a well-stirred solution of phenylaluminium hydride, $\text{AlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(3-n)}$ in equimolar proportions and the reaction mixture stirred at room temperature for approximately 1 hr. The resulting solution was analyzed and infrared spectrum recorded. Results are given in Table 1.

spectrum of LiAlPh_4 in THF showed the presence of two multiplets downfield to the THF multiplet, due to *ortho* and *meta-para* protons of the phenyl groups. The internal chemical shifts, δ int., between the *ortho* (lower multiplets) and *meta-para* (upper multiplet) protons of the phenyl groups were observed to be 0.60 ppm. In the case of phenyllithium, the internal chemical shifts, between the *ortho* and *meta-para* proton multiplets were found to be 0.99 ppm at room temperature while in the case of triphenylaluminium, it was found to be 0.51 ppm. Ladd⁷ has shown that protons *ortho* to the metal-carbon bond in phenylmetallic compounds experience a large deshielding effect. He has further shown that metals of lower electronegativity produce greater deshielding of the *ortho* protons and increased δ int. We have also noticed the same effect in the case of phenyllithium and triphenylaluminium; the former being more electropositive, gave a larger δ int. compared to the more electronegative aluminium.

The redistribution of LiAlH_4 and LiAlPh_4 was studied by adding an ether solution of LiAlH_4 to an ether slurry of LiAlPh_4 in 1:1, 1:3 and 3:1 ratios followed by infrared analysis of the resulting solutions (Fig. 1). When an ether solution of LiAlH_4 was added dropwise to a well stirred slurry of LiAlPh_4 in 1:3 ratio in diethyl ether at room temperature, a clear solution was obtained.

An infrared spectrum of the resulting solution showed the presence of a strong band at 1730 cm^{-1} due to Al-H stretching (LiAlH_4 shows Al-H stretching at 1740 cm^{-1} in diethyl ether). However, when the excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure, a viscous colorless liquid resulted which on standing at room temperature for 5 days gave crystals that analyzed for $\text{LiAlHPh}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$. The infrared spectrum of these crystals dissolved in diethyl ether showed the presence of Al-H stretching

TABLE 1—REACTIONS OF PhLi WITH $\text{AlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(3-n)}$

Exp. No.	Reactants (mmoles) PhLi $\text{AlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(3-n)}$	Solvent (ml)	Analysis (Ratio) Li : Al : H : Ph	Product	IR $\nu\text{Al-H}$ (cm^{-1})
1.	5.5 AlH_3 (5.5)	45	1.03 : 1.00 : 2.92 : 1.05	LiAlH_2Ph	1730
2.	4.5 AlH_2Ph (4.5)	50	1.02 : 1.00 : 1.93 : 2.04	$\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$	1710
3.	5.5 AlHPh_2 (5.5)	55	1.04 : 1.00 : 0.95 : 3.07	LiAlHPh_3	1680

Results and Discussion

In order to study the redistribution of LiAlPh_4 and LiAlH_4 , it was necessary to prepare LiAlPh_4 in the pure state. For this study, LiAlPh_4 was synthesized by the reaction of PhLi with Ph_3Al in diethyl ether and characterized by elemental analysis and X-ray powder diffraction studies. The nmr

at 1730 cm^{-1} . The nmr spectrum of the ether solution showed two multiplets due to *ortho* and *meta-para* protons of the phenyl groups. The internal chemical shift, δ int., was found to be 0.60 ppm.

The product, LiAlHPh_3 , was also prepared by the reaction of PhLi with AlHPh_2 in diethyl ether (Eq. 2). Diphenylaluminium hydride was prepared

by the redistribution reaction of aluminium hydride

with triphenylaluminium in 1:2 ratio in THF as well as in diethyl ether (Eq. 3). In 1964, Surtees⁹ reported the preparation of AlHPh_2 and AlH_2Ph by the

redistribution reaction of AlH_3 and Ph_3Al in the appropriate ratio in refluxing benzene. He reported the nmr spectra of the products in dichloromethane to contain only one set of multiplets due to phenyl protons. However, during our studies in THF solvent, we obtained two sets of multiplets explainable due to the *ortho* and *meta-para* protons of the phenyl groups.

When LiAlH_4 was added to LiAlPh_4 in 1:1 molar ratio, the band due to Al-H stretching shifted to 1710 cm^{-1} . A highly viscous liquid resulted when an excess of solvent was removed under vacuum. However, the viscous liquid produced crystals on standing for 3 days at room temperature. Elemental analysis showed the product to be $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$. The nmr spectrum of an ether solution of $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$ showed two multiplets due to *ortho*

and *meta-para* protons of the phenyl ring; the internal chemical shift was 0.61 ppm.

When the ratio of reacting solutions of LiAlPh_4 to LiAlH_4 was 3:1 in diethyl ether, a broad band centered at 1680 cm^{-1} was observed in the infrared spectrum due to Al-H stretching. When an excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure, a crystalline solid appeared. These crystals were analyzed and were consistent with the compound $\text{LiAlHPh}_3 \cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{O}$. When these crystals were dried under vacuum at $25^\circ/0.05 \text{ mm}$ for 1/2 hr, a viscous liquid resulted which corresponded, by analysis, to $\text{LiAlHPh}_3 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$. When a small amount of ether was added to this viscous liquid, it became crystalline immediately. The infrared spectrum of these crystals in ether showed an Al-H stretching band at 1680 cm^{-1} and the internal chemical shift in the nmr spectrum due to the phenyl ring was found to be 0.62 ppm.

The products $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2$ and LiAlHPh_3 were also prepared by the reactions of phenyllithium with phenylaluminium hydride (PhAlH_2) and AlH_2Ph respectively (Eq. 5). The resulting products exhibited Al-H stretching bands similar to those reported above for the same products prepared by the redistribution of LiAlH_4 and LiAlPh_4 .

All of the $\text{LiAlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(4-n)}$ compounds were soluble in diethyl ether and THF and the solubility in diethyl

ether increased with the number of hydride groups.

The vacuum DTA-TGA data for the $\text{LiAlH}_n\text{Ph}_{(4-n)}$ compounds are given in Table 2. It seems that these products first disproportionate to give LiAlH_4 and LiAlPh_4 and then the LiAlH_4 further decomposes to give Li_3AlH_6 . The detailed decomposition scheme for $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ is given below. (See also Fig. 2.)

TABLE 2—THERMAL DECOMPOSITION OF LITHIUM HYDRIDO-PHENYLALUMINATES.

Compound	Thermicity	Range of transition (peak max), °C	% wt. loss
$\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$	Endo	55-90 (70)	24.2
	Endo	90-120 (98)	20.1
	Exo	170-200 (190)	0.55
	Endo	200-225 (210)	0.55
	Endo	280-350 (320)	40.2
$\text{LiAlH}_3\text{Ph} \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{O}$	Endo	60-125 (90)	56.2
	Exo	165-190 (180)	0.58
	Endo	190-215 (197)	0.28
$\text{LiAlHPh}_3 \cdot 4\text{Et}_2\text{O}$	Endo	270-350 (315)	28.3
	Endo	50-150 (110)	52.1
	Exo	165-195 (185)	0.11
	Endo	195-220 (200)	0.06
	Endo	295-348 (318)	32.3

Fig. 2. Vacuum DTA-TGA of $\text{LiAlH}_2\text{Ph}_2 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$

The trappable gases were identified to be diethyl ether and benzene. It was also determined that when LiAlPh_4 is thermally decomposed under vacuum, it produces biphenyl.

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